

Collaboration between community-led initiatives and local governments: from a wicked problem to effective transformative social innovation?

Extended abstract for the special session on Geography of Sustainability Transitions, included in the fourth Conference of Geography of Innovation (January 31st - February 2nd, 2018, Barcelona)

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“Designing institutional arrangements that help induce successful coproductive strategies is far more daunting than demonstrating their theoretical existence” (*Ostrom, 1996*)

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He has twenty years of experience in leading local participatory sustainability projects, in NGOs, business, universities and local government, in more than 50 communities, creating networks that mobilized around 20,000 citizens and 1,000 organizations. He got some international awards and recognitions, for regional water governance (European Environment Agency, 2014), Environmental Strategic Plan for the Porto Metropolitan Area (ICLEI, 2005) or 100,000 trees project (United Nations, 2014).

The background

The world is changing faster than at any time in human history. The obvious corollary to this statement is that we must also adapt faster than ever. It is not our intention here to discuss this argument, that some consider just a cliché (Frederik, 2016) and others call the “the great acceleration” (Steffen, Broadgate, Deutsch, Gaffney, & Ludwig, 2015).

Faster or not, researchers agree that “many households, communities, organizations, countries, and regions are confronting a confluence of economic, political, demographic, social, cultural, and environmental changes” (IPCC, 2014, p. 1121). Adding climate change and extreme events to the equation, we can conclude that sustainable development is clearly being jeopardized (*idem*).

These changes are also considered by scientists and activists as the necessary impulse and as an opportunity to improve society (Göpel, 2016; Olsson et al., 2006). Naomi Klein, in the documentary “This Changes Everything” (inspired by her bestselling book), asks “What if global warming isn’t only a crisis? What if it’s the best chance we are ever going to get to build a better world?” (Lewis, 2015).

Not surprisingly, a growing body of literature dedicates to the so-called resilience-transition-transformation framework (Markard, Raven, & Truffer, 2012; Pelling, 2011). It has been argued that “a new science on deliberate transformation is needed to both complement and supplement current research on adaptation” (O’Brien, 2012).

Transformation is defined as a “change in the fundamental attributes of natural and human systems” and “benefit from iterative learning, deliberative processes, and innovation” (IPCC, 2014, p. 1122). It may occur in any place, scale, sector, dimension or context, involving “energy and agricultural systems, financial systems, governance regimes, development paradigms, power and gender relations, production and consumption patterns, lifestyles, knowledge production systems, or values and world-views” (O’Brien, 2012). As for any change, barriers and costs are expected (Biesbroek, Klostermann, Termeer, & Kabat, 2013; Kates, Travis, & Wilbanks, 2012).

Besides all the accumulated scientific knowledge about the imperative need of transformation to sustainability and possible pathways, the problem remains. This is considered to be a result of the “failure of sustainability science to engage with the root causes of unsustainability” and the need to “identify solution-oriented approaches to transformational change” (Abson et al., 2017).

Meanwhile, an increasing number of groups of people are proactively and voluntarily joining together in their communities with the focus of “bringing about positive change within their own geographical areas”, contributing to strengthen resilience and sustainability (O’Hara, 2013). These so-called community-led/based initiatives or grassroots movements act on their own initiative, are action oriented and are “emerging in cities, towns, villages and rural areas” (*idem*).

In terms of climate change, they “already have significant and positive roles in support of adaptation planning and decisions” and are ready to be mainstreamed (IPCC, 2014, p. 580). The initiatives providing electricity and heat from renewable sources, sustainable transport and vegetarian meals have the highest potential for climate change mitigation (TESS, 2017).

In any case, we should consider that “there are limits to what community action can do” and even inequality might arise as an unintended result, with “only those local areas with strong levels of social capital being able to benefit most from community-led action” (*idem*).

Recent studies coming from several European research projects demonstrate that interactions between “civil society” and government have “both positive and negative effects (...) and a systematic understanding of both the potential and the tensions of civil society actors in sustainability transitions is currently lacking” (Frantzeskaki et al., 2016). A new research agenda should “adopt a dynamic understanding of the role of civil society” and “conceptualize and empirically explore the dynamic interactions between civil society actors and other actors and elements in the contexts in which they are embedded” (*idem*).

In search of the holy grail: looking for universal tools for local collaborative transformations

Agenda 21 was approved in the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development in 1992 as a global program aiming at sustainable development. It included a call for local action, and in the following years thousands of municipalities worldwide developed their own Local Agenda 21 in a participatory way. As any voluntary policy innovation, it had its dawn and zenith (Pinto, Macedo, Macedo, Almeida, & Silva, 2015).

Local Agenda 21 is considered a good example of a necessary feature of successful regime transformation (Göpel, 2016): “niche alternatives start to develop and gain momentum, coalitions start forming and coalesce around the principles of a new approach”.

Since then other global agendas were approved but any reached this level of local appropriation. In 2015 the “2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development” was adopted, namely the Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2015). It has been stated that science should contribute by facilitating the “local ownership” and the development of “partnerships between academia, business, civil society and governments in order to find innovative sustainable development solutions through networks” (Schmalzbauer & Martin, 2016).

The vision for this research is somehow to contribute to the emergence of a follower to Local Agenda 21, helping to localize the Sustainable Development Goals. The expected results are to find the right framework (and also tools and indicators) that can promote not only a common agenda but mainly local action towards sustainability; a framework that can be operational or even institutional, being simultaneously inspiring and supportive; one that is assumed equally and jointly by local governments and community-led initiatives; one that can be flexible enough to be adapted to an extent of different geographies; one that creates synergies between democratic legitimacy, regulatory power and peoples’ energy, using climate change as a catalyzer.

The research

A recent European report (EEA, 2016) states that stakeholder engagement and public participation are necessary in climate governance but still rare in a meaningful way. It calls for “new ways of collaboration, and innovations in governing” namely “innovative partnerships with private sector and civil society actors”.

In fact, assessing these collaborations is not as straightforward as it might look. Having any kind of collaboration might even be considered undesirable. To start with, we can reason that being institutionally and politically independent is, in fact, the main strength of community-led initiatives (TESS, 2017). On the other hand, “when citizens start putting their ideas and ideals into practice, they organize things in their own way, which may conflict with policy” (van Dam, Salverda, & During, 2014). Participatory climate change governance can be just an illusion (Few, Brown, & Tompkins, 2007).

In the context of the Transition Network we find examples that range from groups of citizens taking over the municipality administration by supporting independent candidates to town councils that completely appropriate the transition action.

Creating networks and partnerships and collaborating with others is considered one of the seven essential ingredients in a transition initiative (Hopkins & Thomas, 2016). Specifically, to “build a bridge to local government” used to be one of the twelve steps, which was considered to be “somewhat of an oxymoron” (Smith, 2011). It has also been described as “endlessly frustrating” but making a “huge difference” (Rowell, 2010).

As a starting point, based on exploratory research, we tried to develop tentative guidelines for designing a multidimensional assessment of collaborations between these local actors. It was concluded that “partnerships for transition” must be cocreated, mutually supportive, innovative and lead to the coproduction of transformative goods and services.

The work in progress includes mapping and assessing experiences in a number of countries; co-designing an agreed framework and a set of tools, training and guidance; testing and refining the agreed framework in pilot areas to develop a shared evidence base; reaching out to decision-makers, practitioners and other stake-holders.

Participatory-action research is used, since it has proven to be valuable in supporting transformative change (Campos et al., 2016).

First results will be shared in the special session, namely the “compass for collaborative transition” (indicators and assessment criteria for participatory climate change governance) and the analyses of experiences across different policy areas and socioeconomic contexts. More significant, we will share the co-designed framework and set of tools chosen to be tested.

Special emphasis will be given to the analysis of how place-specificity matters for transitions, thus hoping to contribute to generalize this knowledge (Hansen & Coenen, 2015).

This effort is integrated with the project “Municipalities in Transition”, which seeks to support systemic change, by fostering values, and frames that encourage a cultural shift from separation to collaboration (Huertas et al., 2017).

The project is currently implemented by Transition Network, in partnership with the group of 31 hubs (regional or national-level organizations). Transition Network (TN) is an international charity based in the United Kingdom “which works to inspire, encourage, connect, support and train communities as they self-organize around the Transition model” (*idem*). The project is financed by KR Foundation (Denmark).

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